

Implementing Co-curricular Activities to Revitalize Entrepreneurial Skills to Primary Schools Pupils in Tanzania

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Abstract

Primary education is a cornerstone and basic foundation for enhancing different skills and knowledge that expose children with opportunities and challenges within the society. This kind of education is implemented through core-curricular, co-curricular, extra-curricular and hidden curricular. While this is true, the majority of primary schools in Tanzania have discouraging performance in the implementation of co-curricular activities that enable pupils to be exposed in various entrepreneurship activities compared as to other countries. In raising the performance, Tanzania is now receiving a considerable attention through its policies to revitalize the implementation of co-curricular activities. In the effort to enhance success in the implementation of co-curricular activities to different primary schools, there is an intervention that currently the government is imposing to revisit the past mistake with an intention of comprehending what has made Tanzania to be where it is today. Thus, the purpose of this study is to examine the implementation of co-curricular activities and its reflection on revitalizing entrepreneurial skills to primary schools pupils in Tanzania. In achieving this study, the concurrent triangulation research design and mixed research approach were employed which included 467 participants. The study was done in Mbeya City and involved 332 pupils, 125 primary school teachers, 8 heads of primary schools and 2 quality assurers. The findings indicate that majority of primary schools in Tanzania are implementing different co-curricular activities which relate to entrepreneurship and pupils gain the entrepreneurial skills and knowledge that are highly useful for them. However, the study findings show that majority of private primary schools had good system of enhancing entrepreneurial skills to primary school pupils as compared to public primary schools in Tanzania. From the base of these findings it is concluded that implementing co-curricular activities in primary schools plays a vital role in revitalizing entrepreneurial skills that are useful to pupils and enable them to secure different opportunities after completion of primary education level. Therefore, it is recommended that, school owners whether private or public primary schools should emphasise the implementation of co-curricular activities and accord them similar status with core-curricula programs with an intention of developing a pupil in cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains.

Key Words: Primary Education, Co-curricular Activities, Entrepreneurial Skills and Pupils

Introduction

The implementation of co-curricular activities involves the pupil practical oriented components of the curriculum occurring in the whole process of learning that enable pupils to grasp what they learn during class hours and connect them with other skills that are grasped and gained outside class hours (Ieorge & Thinguni, 2013; Coven, 2015; MoEST, 2016). These activities include music, arts, drama, sports and games, debate, subject clubs and vocational clubs. It is proved that co-curricular activities are as old as the education system itself and they can be traced back in the

era of ancient Greece, China, India and Near East (Wuest & Bucher, 1999). These activities during that era aimed at maintaining religious issues, survival, health, active life, recreation and defence (Ndee, 2010; Wuest & Bucher, 1999). Later on, majority of the co-curricular activities were included in school curricula with intention of meeting the benefits developed through implementation of these activities (Coven, 2015; Broh, 2012).

Various co-curricular activities were implemented in different countries worldwide with intention of saving different purpose to learners. For example, the United States of America (USA) implemented the co-curricular activities such as quiz bowls, musical groups, sports, games, student governments, school newspapers, science fairs, debate teams and clubs focusing on academic areas with intention of enriching different skills that enable their child to reflect the actual practical situations of what happened in the society (Storey, 2010; Haber, 2006; Dhanmeher, 2014). England has been implementing co-curricular activities such as sports and games, debates, subject clubs and pupils' organisations as an integral part of pupils' learning process and an essential mechanism for developing the psychological and intellectual abilities of learners (George & Thinguni, 2013; Coven, 2015). In Nepal, they believed that implementing co-curricular activities reinforces the whole process of learning to learners.

In East Africa, Kenya in particular, several schools has reported co-curricular activities to have achieved better results in various areas of learning (Wangai, 2012). Through co-curricular activities, pupils attain various skills such as creative problem solving, entrepreneurship, sports, games, cooperation, communication and leadership (Ndirangu, 2015). Uganda is also implementing co-curricular activities because believed that it prepare learners in all domains. In Tanzania, co-curricular activities hold a place of great importance in the field of education for developing different careers to learners (Shehu, 2001; Mafumiko & Pangani, 2008; Japhet, 2010; Makwinya & Straton, 2014; Lazaro & Anney, 2016). The Ministry of Education has insisted the implementation of co-curricular activities in and outside the schools since pre-colonial education, whereby children participated in informal co-curricular activities such as swimming, dancing, singing and playing by considering the experiences of the surrounding culture and they were informally acquired (Mafumiko & Pangani, 2008; Ndee, 2010). During colonial period, co-curricular activities were done in schools, whereby different sports and games were practiced (Kazungu, 2010; Machera, 2012).

After independence, the government of Tanzania adopted and implemented co-curricular activities in schools (MoEC, 1995). Various policies such as Education for Self-Reliance (ESR) of 1967; Education and Training Policy of 1995 and 2014; Basic Education Curricular for pre-primary, primary and secondary education, as well as curriculum for teachers education were supposed to be implemented parallel with co-curricular activities (MoEC, 1967 & 1995; MoEVT 2014; MoEST, 2016; Lazaro, 2015). The government of Tanzania has also placed a strong emphasis on quality environment that aims at improving learning process and environment that enhances pupils' learning outcomes (MoEC, 1995 & MoEVT, 2014). For example, the

Education and Training Policy (ETP) of 1995 insists on preparing the pupils with the foundation of self-creativity, self-advancement and self-confidence, which help them to enter into the world of work (MoEC, 1995 & MoEVT, 2014).

With progressive emphases, it is therefore, justified that implementing co-curricular activities in schools is seen as the way of laying the foundations for instilling different principles, skills, knowledge, social aspects and attitudes patterning to entrepreneurship that stimulate and consolidate learning. It is from this background that prompted the researcher to investigate the role of co-curricular activities in revitalizing the entrepreneurship skills to majority of primary schools in Mbeya City in Tanzania.

Statement of the problem

Apart of the revealed importance that have been attached to co-curricular activities in schools, the implementation of co-curricular activities in majority of primary schools are increasingly neglected (Makwinya & Straton 2014; Juma 2015; Lazaro & Anney, 2016). These studies show that, some practitioners argue that implementing co-curricular activities is time consuming and wastage of learning time. They insist on teaching the core curricula subjects that are evaluated through the National Examinations Council of Tanzania (NECTA) (Juma, 2015). This perspective illustrates that co-curricular activities are undervalued. Thus, this study examined the implementation of co-curricular activities and its role of revitalizing entrepreneurial skills to primary schools pupils in Tanzania.

The purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine the implementation of co-curricular activities and its role of revitalizing the entrepreneurial skills to pupils of primary schools in Tanzania.

The Significance of the Study

The findings of this study add both theoretical and practical knowledge to the available literature on the implementation of co-curricular activities in primary schools in Tanzania. Theoretically, the study contributes in filling the research gaps by revealing the current situation of implementing co-curricular activities in primary schools and its role of revitalizing the entrepreneurial skills to pupils of primary schools. Also, the findings may serve as an insight and reference for further research on co-curriculum in primary education in Tanzania and in other countries.

The Limitation of the Study

The findings of this study came from teachers, heads of schools, teachers, pupils and quality assurers; therefore, it is possible that some respondents gave responses that pleased their authorities as opposed to the real perception regarding the implementation of co-curricular activities in primary schools. However, this limitation was solved by using multiple data collection tools, creating good rapport with participants and assuring them of confidentiality. Another limitation was dearth of relevant literature related to the implementation of co-curricular

activities in primary schools in Tanzania. In this case, the study lacked sufficient local literature and forced the researcher to use literature beyond the primary schools context in Tanzania. However, the surveyed literature was sufficient and it helped in identifying the gap that this study intended to fill.

Research Design

The study employed concurrent triangulation mixed research design. The design was used because it focused on collecting, analyzing, interpreting and reporting concurrently both quantitative and qualitative data. The central premise of using this design was to develop better understanding of a research problem being investigated rather than using a single approach (Creswell & Clark, 2011). The design helped the researcher to concurrently collect both qualitative and quantitative data, analyse, interpret and report the data at the same time (Onwuegbuzie et al, 2007).

Sampling Techniques

This study used purposive and stratified random sampling techniques in selecting the appropriate sample for the study as explained in the following subsections.

Purposive sampling technique

Purposive sampling technique was used to select Mbeya City. Mbeya City was selected because of its strategic location of being the heart of the region. The city has an appropriate number of public and primary schools compared to other districts in Mbeya region. This was the target of this study. Hence, Mbeya City provided all the necessary information that was required for the development of this study. Moreover, the city was purposively chosen because it comprises many government offices including the quality assurance district and zonal offices that have the profile for quality assurers.

Additionally, purposive sampling technique was used in selecting district educational officer, heads of school, teachers and experts from quality assurance office at the zonal and district level. All aforementioned respondents were selected because of their administrative roles and responsibilities of implementing and organising primary education at the district and school levels.

Stratified Random Sampling

Stratified random sampling technique was used to select eight (8) primary schools from the strata of public and private schools. The advantage of using stratified random sampling is that it increases the likelihood and equal representativeness of the sample, and ensures that all key characteristics of individuals in the population are involved. The strata were based on the type of primary school ownership because, as per government policy, all primary schools are required to implement co-curricular activities. After dividing the schools based on ownership, they were randomly selected in the strata of public and private schools.

Similarly, stratified random sampling technique was used to select primary school pupils of standard five and six based on gender (Male & Female) from both the public and the private primary schools. The reason for selecting standard five and six pupils was based on the directives of primary school curriculum that specified the kind of co-curricular activities that are to be implemented to standard five and six. Also, the researcher believed that standard five and six pupils are matured enough to provide relevant information on the actual situation in primary schools compared to other lower primary school levels. In each sampled school, fifty (50) pupils (25 boys & 25 girls) were selected. To get five (25) boys in each class the researcher prepared ten (50) cards numbered (1) or (2) that were placed in the container and every card was randomly selected by standard five and six boys. The same procedure was done to girls. After that, a child who picked a card showing number two (2) had a chance to take part in the study

Sample Size

The study population was grouped in two strata based on the type of school ownership in terms of public and private ownership. It is advised that sample size should match with the size of population of which the results are to be considered representative (Cohen, *et al.* 2006; Kombo & Tromp, 2006). Taking a larger sample than necessary is to waste time while taking small sample makes the results to be of less practical use (Kothari, 2004). On the basis of the number of the study population, a total of 535 participants were selected. As for teachers 10% of the target population was selected. In this regard, primary school teachers who were 1225, the selected sample was 125 respondents. As for primary school pupils of standard five and six, who were 19860, the formula proposed by Israel (2013) was used to select pupils of standard five and six to be involved in this study. The formula is based on 95% confidence level and $p=0.05$ read as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Whereby ‘n’ is the sample size to be calculated; ‘N’ is the total population of the study; ‘e’ the level of precision or margin of error measured by probability scale of 5%. Therefore, plugging data into the formula, the following was in order:

$$\{\text{Whereby } n=? \quad N=19860; \quad e=0.05\}$$

$$n = \frac{19860}{1 + 19860(0.05)^2}$$

$$\text{Therefore, } n \text{ (pupils)} = 400$$

The study required both primary and secondary data which were based on qualitative and quantitative approaches. The reasons of collecting the data from both qualitative and quantitative approaches was to help the researcher to triangulate and confirm the finding by complementing one evidence with another evidence from different sources of data. This is supported by Ulin (2002) who notes that there is no single method that can provide the answers to research problems in all dimensions. Therefore, in this study the researcher applied four data collection methods, namely; interview, observation, documentary review and questionnaires

Data Analysis Procedures

Data collected in this study were analysed both qualitatively and quantitatively. As for qualitative data, the data that were collected in the field were analysed through content analysis. In this study, the analysis involved the extraction of the relevant data that was collected from the field and then compressed, organised and assembled. Finally conclusion was drawn and verification was done. Furthermore, the collected data was coded and categorized in accordance with the research objectives and the respondents' arguments were presented through direct verbatim quotations. The use of content analysis indicated that it is a dynamic form of analysing verbal and visual data that are oriented on summarising the informational content of the data (Onwuegbuzie & Byers, 2014; Onwuegbuzie & Leech, 2005; Morgan, 1993). On the other hand, the quantitative data from questionnaires were analysed with the help of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 20. The collected data were subjected to descriptive statistical analysis with interpretation that was given in terms of frequencies, percentages, mean scores and standard deviations. Finally, both qualitative and quantitative findings were mixed together during presentation, analysis and discussion of the results in order to corroborate.

Findings and Discussions

The current study was guided by one research questions. The findings of the study are presented as per the study questions and items of the questionnaire. The study question was: What are the co-curricular activities related to entrepreneurship being implemented in primary schools and how does the implemented co-curricular activities related entrepreneurship help to revitalize the entrepreneurial skills to primary schools pupils? The findings and discussion are presented as follows.

The Implemented Entrepreneurship Activities in Primary Schools

In this category the purpose was to identify the co-curricular activities that relate to entrepreneurship activities, which were implemented in primary schools by reflecting the 2005 curriculum of primary schools and the Education and Training Policy of 1995 and 2014 in Tanzania. The entrepreneurship activities that were targeted by the researcher as per the curriculum of primary schools were gardening, farming, weaving, toy making, basket making, spinning, tailoring and kitting. The first item required the respondents to indicate whether they had entrepreneurship activities in their schools. The findings from pupils' questionnaires indicated that majority of primary schools pupils (254, 76.5%) agreed that entrepreneurship activities were implemented as co-curricular activities in their schools. In contrast, findings from teachers' questionnaire showed that although entrepreneurship activities were implemented in primary schools, there were variations between public and private primary schools. In public primary schools, entrepreneurship activities were rarely implemented as co-curricular activities where as in private primary schools entrepreneurship activities were well implemented.

Furthermore, the researcher conducted an interview to heads of schools who were asked to respond on availability of entrepreneurship activities in their schools. In responding to this item,

some schools heads said that some entrepreneurship activities were implemented and pupils participated as part of learning process. On this note, one head of school said that:

...In my school, I insist to implement different entrepreneurship activities such as gardening, farming, weaving and pot making on a weekly basis. This is allocated in the school daily routine... **Source:** Field Data (August, 2018)

The above excerpt implies that some primary schools implemented various entrepreneurship activities as part of co-curricular activities.

On the other hand, other heads of schools said that entrepreneurship activities were not implemented because of limited school timetable, environment and challenges of facilities and equipment, which did not favour for implementation of some activities. In affirming this one head of public primary school was quoted saying:

...In this place we have two public primary schools, ours is the oldest school built in 2010. It was divided into two and now we have two primary schools in the same place. This does not allow us to introduce even a garden for vegetable. So, it is difficult to implement the entrepreneurship activities like farming, gardening, kitting etc... may be the schools that are located in rural areas may be doing those activities...Schools like ours, which are located in town it is very difficult to have such activities... **Source:** Field Data, (September, 2018)

The above quotation implies that some primary schools failed to implement co-curricular activities due to limited school environment and time. Because of this pupils had limited place for learning various activities associated with entrepreneurship activities. In regard to these findings, it could be said that besides the school curriculum insistence on having entrepreneurship activities, some surveyed schools did not have these activities. It was also noticed through documentary review that there were marked differences on the way public primary schools implemented the entrepreneurship activities compared to private primary schools as indicated in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1 Implemented Entrepreneurship Activities in Primary Schools

Types of Subject Club	Implemented entrepreneurship activities	
	Public Schools	Private Schools
Gardening	✓	✓
farming	x	✓
Weaving	✓	✓
Basket making	x	✓
Spinning	x	✓
Tailoring	✓	✓
Kitting	✓	✓

Source: Field Data (September, 2018)

Table 1.1 indicates that there were some inconsistencies in the implementation of co-curricular activities related to entrepreneurship in primary schools. Majority of private primary schools had all proposed entrepreneurship activities such as gardening, farming, weaving, basket making, spinning, tailoring and kitting activities. While in public primary schools there were gardening, weaving, tailoring and kitting activities. This implies that private primary schools implemented all proposed entrepreneurship activities while public primary schools implemented four out of the seven entrepreneurship activities.

Furthermore, quality assurers were interviewed on whether entrepreneurship activity was implemented as a co-curricular activity in primary schools. In responding to this item, the quality assurers revealed that entrepreneurship activities were implemented in schools. However, not all primary schools managed to implement all the types of entrepreneurship activities proposed by the primary school curriculum. They indicated that when inspecting different schools they also observed entrepreneurship activities like project activities. Through this process they found out that some schools implemented all entrepreneurship activities while others did not. For instance, one quality assurer was quoted saying:

...These activities are implemented in some primary schools especially private primary schools where they regard these activities as a self-reliance education. However, some public primary schools do not implement all proposed entrepreneurship activities as per curriculum...**Source:** Field Data (August, 2018)

The above quotation implies that entrepreneurship activities were implemented in primary schools though some of schools did not implement all proposed activities by the primary schools curriculum.

The findings from various methods of data collection establish that entrepreneurship activities are implemented in schools, although the magnitude of implementation varied from private to public primary schools. These findings concur with those of Machera (2012), Juma (2015) and Lazaro (2015), who noticed that majority of the entrepreneurship activities such as project activities were implemented in many urban schools where students learned different production activities. Also, in a similar study, Machera (2012) indicated that in the years before 1995 majority of public primary schools had entrepreneurship programmes like school shop, farming activities, and other project activities. However, later they were abolished and efforts were vested in core-subject taught in schools. Therefore, this argument supports the finding of this study especially in the public primary schools where it was witnessed by the researcher to be selective in the implementation of entrepreneurship activities compared to private primary schools.

Theoretically, the findings of this study reveal that majority of primary school implemented the co-curricular activities. So, the findings are in line with the proposed view of the open system theory, which believes that the school system survives if their desired goals align with the environmental needs by considering the input, transformational process and output. According to

this theory the input meant the resources that are received from the external environment and transformational process are the resources within a system while output are the value added or product that are exported back to the environment as the feedback (Thien & Razak, 2012). In this regard, the findings of this study indicated that the implementation process of entrepreneurship activities was dependent on the inputs (available resources) in the school environment. Since private schools had enough resources it was possible to implement all proposed entrepreneurship activities.

The role of entrepreneurship activities in revitalizing entrepreneurial skills to pupils

In this aspect the intention was to understand whether co-curricular activities related to entrepreneurship activities contributed to provision of entrepreneurship skills to primary schools pupils. The information that responded to this category was collected through questionnaires that were administered to pupils and teachers. The data that were presented through open ended questionnaire that were administered to teachers indicated that majority of teachers 92% replied that through implementing co-curricular activities that related to entrepreneurship activities enabled pupils to gain different skills of recognizing the business opportunities, developing specific local knowledge and knowing the networking system of production.

Also pupils were required to respond through Likert Scale that was administered with the scale aspect of Strong Disagree (SD), Strong Agreed (SA) and Neutral (N). The responses are presented in Table 1.2 below:

Table1.2: Pupils responses on the role of entrepreneurship activities in schools

Items	SD	N	SA
• Participating in co-curricular related to entrepreneurship activities help you in raising awareness on various production opportunities	95%	2%	3%
• Participating in co-curricular related to entrepreneurship activities gives an opportunity to be creative and gain the recognition skills	85%	10%	5%
• Through participating in co-curricular related to entrepreneurship activities help in gaining specific local skills that connect with your environment	98%	1%	1%
• Participating in co-curricular related to entrepreneurship activities help in identification of business opportunities that will enable in establishing a business after finishing your studies	75%	14%	11%

The findings as indicated in Table 1.2, implies that majority of pupils were very positive with the implementation of co-curricular activities that relates with co-curricular activities. Majority of pupils recognized that through participating in those activities were in position of acquiring different entrepreneurial skills through being aware with various entrepreneurial opportunities, being active and creative, and they gained different local skills that enable them to understand the productive activities in their surrounding environment.

Generally, the findings in this item are in line with the findings of Linan (2004) who noted that if we want to reach in larger part of development, entrepreneurship education should integrate substantial awareness content through developing intention, creativity and business knowledge that would be the most relevant way to our learners. Also, in the study of Lazaro and Anney (2016) insisted that participating in co-curricular activities increased an opportunity of realizing various production opportunities that in the long run enabled the learners to grasp different opportunities that surround in the local environment. This finding implies that through participating in different co-curricular activities that relate to entrepreneurship activities pupils gain different knowledge and skills that relate to identification of various opportunities of developing business and other productive activities that enable them to secure opportunities after completing their studies. This intention is in aligning with the Tanzania 2025 vision and the Sustainable Development Goal of 2030 that insist on eradicating ignorance to majority of Africans including Tanzania through giving them the education that is practical oriented.

Conclusion

Despite the government directive and policies on implementation of co-curricular that relate to entrepreneurship activities in all schools, the implementation process varies between public and private primary schools. More co-curricular that relate to entrepreneurship activities are implemented in private primary schools than in public primary schools. Therefore, the findings of this study proposed that there should be a balance in terms of implementation for both private and public primary schools.

Recommendation

For the aim of developing a pupil who learns holistically in primary education, there is a need for integrating the co-curricular that relate to entrepreneurship activities in the school curricula as compulsory programmes that make all educational stakeholders value and implement in schools. Likewise, it is essential to emphasise the implementation of co-curricular that relate to entrepreneurship activities in all teacher training colleges and universities so as once teachers are employed, they can be able to implement well all school programmes including co-curricular activities.

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